

RESIST

Fostering Queer Feminist Intersectional Resistances against Transnational Anti-Gender Politics

The Prevalence of Anti-LGBTIQ+ and Anti-Feminist Sentiment and Mobilisations in Ireland

RESIST Survey Findings from Ireland, August 2024 & May 2025

Kath Browne, Órlaith Hennessy, Theresa Schilling

UNIVERSITÉ DE FRIBOURG
UNIVERSITÄT FREIBURG

Lucerne University of
Applied Sciences and Arts

HOCHSCHULE
LUZERN

Funded by
the European Union

PUBLICATION INFORMATION

TITLE	The Prevalence of Anti-LGBTIQ+ and Anti-Feminist Sentiment and Mobilisations in Ireland: RESIST Survey Findings from Ireland, August 2024 & May 2025
AUTHORS	Kath Browne, Órlaith Hennessy, Theresa Schilling
DATE	2025
PUBLISHER	RESIST Project
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15776376
COPYRIGHTS	Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International

HOW TO CITE	<i>Kath Browne, Órlaith Hennessy, Theresa Schilling. (2025). The Prevalence of Anti-LGBTIQ+ and Anti-Feminist Sentiment and Mobilisations in Ireland: RESIST Survey Findings from Ireland, August 2024 & May 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15776376</i>
--------------------	--

OUTPUT TYPE	Report
OTHER INFO	RESIST Work Package 2 – Effects of Anti-Gender: Lived Experiences and Everyday Resistances
OUTPUTS REPOSITORY	https://zenodo.org/communities/resistproject/
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://theresistproject.eu/
FUNDING	Funded by the European Union under project no: 101060749. EU Horizon Europe (EU partners); UK Government Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme (UK partner); Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (Swiss partners).
ACKNOWLEDGMENT	Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or British and Swiss funding authorities. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
Introduction	5
Survey Findings	6
Majority supports addressing gender-based violence, and supports LGBTIQ+ rights and abortion	6
Increased targeting of LGBTIQ+ people and women	6
Targeting based on political views is broadly felt	8
Conclusion	9

Executive Summary

Anti-LGBTIQ+ and anti-feminist mobilisations are an increasing part of the Irish landscape. Using a representative quantitative survey, run in August 2024 and repeated in May 2025, this research found that:

- A majority supports the addressing of gender-based violence, and supports LGBTIQ+ rights and abortion.
- However, there is recognition, and experiences, of increased targeting and discrimination against women and LGBTIQ+ people, especially trans people.
- Experiences of targeting and discrimination differ depending on whether you are LGBTIQ+, a woman and/or supportive of abortion rights; however, social division negatively affects all sides of the spectrum of political views on sexualities and genders.

Introduction

'Anti-gender' political mobilisation, including anti-LGBTIQ+¹ and anti-feminisms, have been an increasing part of the Irish landscape, according to activists and others affected by it². This report explores the perceptions of its prevalence and increase in frequency evident in the results of two quantitative RESIST³ Irish case study surveys conducted across Ireland in August 2024 and May 2025. Both runs sampled a representative group of adults living in the Republic of Ireland, with a total of 2,001 individuals participating⁴. They offer important understandings of the treatment of women and LGBTIQ+ people, as well as understandings of how these groups are targeted in contemporary Ireland. 'Anti-gender' is ill-defined and is used here to denote anti-LGBTIQ+, anti-feminist movements in Ireland.

¹ 'LGBTIQ+' is used in this report when referring to the broader population of lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, intersex, queer, and other non-cisgender and non-straight people. 'LGBQ' is used when referring to respondents who identified as lesbian, gay, bisexual and queer in this data, as detailed in footnote 4 and footnote 6.

² Browne, Kath and Hennessy, Órlaith. (2024). The RESIST Project Report. Effects of, and Resistances to 'Anti-Gender' Mobilisations Across Europe: A Report on Ireland. RESIST Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13135784>

³ RESIST is an EU funded Horizon Europe project (EU Project ID 101060749). It explores anti-gender mobilisations, their effects and queer feminist resistances to them.

⁴ The data in this report was collected through two runs of a representative survey undertaken with a representative sample provided by Amárach Research. The data used is weighted. Respondents who identified as women made up 50% (n=504) of the first sample, those who identified as men made up 49% (n=487) and respondents who identified as trans, non-binary or other genders made up 1% (n=11). In the second sample, respondents who identified as women made up 51% (n=511), those who identified as men made up 48% (n=478) and respondents who identified as trans, non-binary or other genders made up 1% (n=13). In terms of sexual orientation, in the first sample, 9% (n=86) of all respondents identified as lesbian, gay, bisexual or queer (LGBQ), 86% (n=860) identified as heterosexual and 6% (n=59) identified as 'other' or preferred not to disclose. In the second sample, 9% (n=93) of all respondents identified as LGBQ, 87% (n=874) identified as heterosexual and 3% (n=34) identified as 'other' or preferred not to disclose. In the first sample, 75% (n=8) of respondents who identified as trans, non-binary or other also identified as lesbian, gay, bisexual, queer or 'other' (LGBQ). In the second sample, all respondents who identified as trans, non-binary or 'other' identified as LGBQ, indicating a complete overlap between these demographics in the latter survey. While this survey was designed to be representative of the general population, the number of respondents who identified as lesbian, gay, bisexual, queer, trans, non-binary or other sexualities and genders was relatively small. As such, these samples may not fully capture the diversity of LGBTIQ+ experiences and identities in Ireland.

Survey Findings

Majority supports addressing gender-based violence, and supports LGBTIQ+ rights and abortion

The vast majority of respondents believe that gender-based violence is a critical issue that requires greater attention and resources.

83% of respondents agree that gender-based violence is a critical issue that needs more attention and resources, in both 2025 (n=833) and 2024 (n=834). Overall findings highlight a widespread recognition of gender-based violence as a significant and urgent issue requiring increased focus and support, though responses indicate slightly stronger agreement among women (89%, n=454) as compared to men (78%, n=372); data from respondents identifying as trans, non-binary or other genders are limited and thus not separately reported, though their perspectives remain vital⁵.

A large majority supports trans rights and this majority is greater among 'LGBQ' people.

The majority of respondents express support for trans people (69%, n=689), agreeing that trans rights are human rights, this percentage staying stable across the two surveys. However, 20% (n=196) disagreed in 2024 and 18% (n=182) in 2025, indicating that now nearly one in five do not recognise trans rights as fundamental human rights. While recognition of trans rights remains steady among approximately two-thirds of heterosexual respondents (67%, n=582), an even larger and increasing majority of LGBQ respondents endorse these rights (88% in 2025, n=82; 85% in 2024, n=72)⁶.

Most respondents believe that access to safe and legal abortion services is a vital aspect of health care.

82% (n=823) of respondents agree that accessing safe and legal abortion services is an essential component of health care, reflecting growing public support for reproductive rights since the two-thirds majority victory in the 2018 referendum.

Increased targeting of LGBTIQ+ people and women

Half of women see a recent increase in the targeting of women.

⁵ In response to the question 'What is your gender? Please select all that apply', respondents could select *woman, man, trans, non-binary* and/or *other*. Out of 2,001 respondents, only 11 identified as *trans*, 13 as *non-binary*, and 2 as *other*. Due to these small sample sizes, their responses cannot be considered representative, and any related insights, while notable, should not be generalised.

⁶ Data on respondents' sexualities and data on their genders were collected independently. In response to the question 'What is your sexual orientation/identification? Please select all that apply', respondents could select *lesbian, gay, bisexual, queer, heterosexual, other*, and/or *prefer not to answer*. Those who selected *lesbian, gay, bisexual* and/or *queer* are represented as 'LGBQ' in these findings.

41% (n=405) of respondents think that there has been a recent increase in targeting of women, but this is felt among women (50%, n=256) more than it is among men (31%, n=149). Roughly a fifth of men surveyed (22%, n=105) think that the targeting of women has reduced recently, compared to just over a tenth of women (12%, n=60).

Targeting of LGBQ people is increasing.

Most LGBQ people who responded have experienced discrimination or unfair treatment on the basis of their sexual orientation and their gender, with the frequency of these encounters increasing over the past year.

The surveys show that around one tenth (11% in 2024, n=110, and in 2025, n=117) of respondents have been discriminated against or treated unfairly in the past year because of their sexual orientation/identification. Revealingly, half of LGBQ people who responded in 2025 (51%, n=48) said they have been discriminated against for this reason, which is an increase from August 2024 (42%, n=35). In 2025 8% (n=67) of heterosexual people said they have been discriminated against for this reason.

In August 2024, a majority of LGBQ respondents (53%, n=46) reported never experiencing gender-based discrimination or unfair treatment, while 31% (n=26) said it happened sometimes and 7% (n=7) often or very often. By May 2025, a majority of LGBQ respondents (56%, n=53) said they had experienced such discrimination; over a third (36%, n=34) reported sometimes experiencing it, and a fifth (20%, n=19) said it occurred often or very often, reflecting an escalating frequency over the last year. In contrast, most heterosexual respondents reported no such experiences, with percentages remaining relatively stable across the two survey iterations (65% in 2025, n=568; 68% in 2024, n=587). Among the small number of respondents who are trans, non-binary or identify as other genders, rates of gender-based discrimination are even higher, with 85% (n=11) reporting having faced such discrimination sometimes, often or very often in the past year.

Half of LGBQ respondents see a rise in the targeting of LGBQ people.

Over half of LGBQ respondents (55%, n=51) think there has been a recent increase in the targeting of lesbians, gay people, bisexual people and other sexual minorities, compared to around a third of heterosexual people (35%, n=306); overall, 37% (n=366) of people have observed such an increase.

A slightly lower percentage indicated a perceived increase in the targeting of lesbians, gay people, bisexual people and other sexual minorities in May 2025, as compared to August 2024: among LGBQ people, it reduced from 59%, n=49, to 55% n=51. This should be read alongside the *increase* in targeting of trans people.

Targeting of trans people is seen to have increased.

Half of all respondents (49%) see a recent increase in the targeting of trans people.

Alongside the significant support for trans rights in this research, there is an awareness of the increase in targeting trans people. A significant proportion—half of respondents (49%,

n=487)—have observed a recent increase in the targeting of trans people; compared to 12% (n=129) who observe that this targeting has decreased. Such an increase was noted more by LGBTQ people specifically (65%, n=61) than by heterosexual people (48%, n=415).

The majority of LGBTQ respondents feel that they are targeted for views on feminism and LGBTQ+ people's rights.

A large majority of LGBTQ respondents (71%) experience hostility because of their political views on feminism or LGBTQ+ people's rights compared to 30% of heterosexual respondents.

A third of respondents (33%, n=330) have experienced hostility because of their political views in relation to feminism or LGBTQ+ peoples rights, and a similar number (32%, n=324) *worry* about experiencing this hostility. More women (38%, n=193) than men (26%, n=127) and the majority of the small number of respondents who are trans, non-binary or other genders (92%, n=12) said they have experienced this hostility. The percentage of LGBTQ people experiencing this hostility (71%, n=66) is higher than that of heterosexual people (30%, n=258), and has increased since 2024 (59%, n=51). More LGBTQ people also *worry* about experiencing this hostility (69%, n=64) than did in 2024 (61%, n=52) and at over double the rate of heterosexual people (28%, n=250). In terms of differences across age groups, almost double the percentage of 18-24 year olds (40%, n=44) as compared to 55+ year olds (21%, n=75) have experienced hostility because of their political views on feminism or LGBTQ+ people's rights.

Targeting based on political views is broadly felt

While there are differences in the experiences of discrimination, targeting and gender-based violence, with a greater impact felt by LGBTQ+ people and women, there is a feeling of hostility across the spectrum of political views in this area, indicating the negative effects of social division.

The data in these surveys points to the negative effect of division around sexuality and gender for many respondents, where the level of hostility reported to be experienced by people with political views in support of abortion access, trans rights and the rights of same-sex couples (40%, n=149) is at a similar level for those with opposing views (32%, n=151). This same pattern is also apparent in the level of *worry* about experiencing hostility because of political views in relation to feminism or LGBTQ+ people's rights. This does not mean that these experiences are the same, but it does indicate that division in these areas is experienced in ways perceived as hostile.

The increase in hostilities reported in the data above indicates that LGBTQ+ people and women experience violence and discrimination and are more likely to be targeted for who they are, as well as their political views.

Conclusion

This research demonstrates that there is broad support for LGBTIQ+ people, women's rights and abortion. This exists alongside a rise in the targeting of these groups and of those who support them. The reported levels of hostility experienced by individuals across the spectrum of political views on sexualities and genders, as well as the widespread concerns about such hostility, highlight the impact of anti-LGBTIQ+ mobilisations and anti-feminisms in Ireland. The escalating divisions regarding sexualities and gender issues negatively affect individuals across this political spectrum, but have particularly significant implications for the safety, wellbeing, and rights of LGBTIQ+ people and women living in Ireland.

The findings presented in this report do not fully capture the diverse and intersecting experiences of racialisation, immigration, disability, social class, or other factors that can significantly influence how individuals experience hostility, violence, and discrimination related to sexuality, gender, and political views. Further research is needed to establish this nuance and prevalence. However, the insights offered, such as the reported increase in perceptions and experiences of the targeting of LGBTIQ+ individuals, particularly trans people, and rising experiences of sexuality and gender-based discrimination, highlight important trends that warrant further attention and research.